

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

BEST PRACTICES ON LEADERSHIP CHARACTERISTICS TO SUPPORT SMART WORKING PHILOSOPHY [SMART WEST]

SPOKE 4 – DIGITAL INNOVATION TOWARD SUSTAINABLE MOUNTAIN

DELIVERABLE 10

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Contents

1. Introduction – 2. Background – PART I – Empirical analysis – 3. Overview – 4. Context of analysis – 5. Data and methods – PART II – Case studies – 6. Alfa – 7. Beta – 8. Gamma – 9. Delta – 10. Theta. – 11. Synthesis and implications.

1. Introduction

The SMART WEST project would like to provide analyses, best practices, intervention lines, tools, and devices to fully exploit the potential of agile and remote working to enhance business performance and improve worker well-being and enable companies to organize these models of work effectively and orderly in the mountain areas of the NODES ecosystem, including the southern regions participating in the project, as Basilicata.

From the point of view of organizational change¹ the application of agile and remote working requires not only a review of processes, work practices and organizational structure but also a cultural evolution and the creation of a collaboration system based on trust, flexibility, autonomy and the enhancement and improvement of employee skills. This requires renewed management practices and leadership skills.

Within this perspective, the research team developed an intensive on-desk literature review activity in the first year of the project (2023), aimed at analyzing the trends regarding challenges and opportunities in agile and remote working, as well as the characteristics and skills required for entrepreneurs and managers to lead organizations in remote working contexts and, more generally, to effectively navigate the Digital Transformation (DT) scenario. The results of the literature review were described in the report "Mapping leadership characteristics: Analysis of the trends in leadership characteristics for organizations adopting remote working"². Regarding leadership characteristics, the literature suggests a set of skills ranging from personal to professional skills needed for leadership in agile and remote work, such as emotional intelligence, competence and adaptability, communication, problem-solving skills, trust and relationship-building, technology skills and data literacy, inclusivity skills, trustworthiness, and a goal-oriented mindset.

Building upon the findings and insights presented in the above-mentioned report, and in line with the project objectives, the research team has developed, in 2024, an empirical on-field analysis of the perceptions, awareness, implementation, and concrete use of remote working practices, as well as of the leadership characteristics capable of effectively supporting the smart working philosophy.

Methodologically, a multiple-case studies approach was adopted, based on data and information collected through official secondary sources and direct interviews with entrepreneurs, CEOs, and top managers of five outstanding companies headquartered in Basilicata that have adopted remote working practices.

It is important to highlight that, as observed through interviews and discussions with institutional representatives (e.g., Confindustria Basilicata, Federmanager Basilicata), the use of remote working appears still limited in the Basilicata region, and it does not seem to be a trend towards increased utilization. The study, therefore, focused on researching and analyzing the significant productive realities that systematically use remote working practices.

¹ Flagship project 1, Research module 4

² NODES - Nord Ovest Digitale E Sostenibile - SPOKE4, Flagship Project 1 - Research Module 4, SMART WEST- Innovative smart working, new digital compliance procedures, and new digital organizational models for Northwest Italian territories

The empirical analysis confirmed that the need to create and maintain a competitive edge - successfully dealing with the rapid technological changes - is forcing organizations to embark DT. In this context, remote work is seen as a fundamental pillar of a DT strategy where a distributed but strongly engaged workforce can play a significant role in guaranteeing and renewing business operations in increasingly challenging environments.

It is also confirmed that successful DT transformation results from the matching and the integration of leadership characteristics, hard and soft skills, mindsets and commitment of people, and the opportunities provided by complex digital tools to increase value for companies and stakeholders.

Building upon the findings of the framework elaborated in the first report, this second report explores the notions of transactional, transformational, entrepreneurial and wise leaders which are some distinctive leadership styles to navigate an organisational transformation. These styles represent the leader's capacities to activate, support, and manage the processes involved in transforming an organization.

Specifically, the empirical analysis highlights the advantages and the risks of agile and remote working, distinguishing the perspectives of analysis and considering separately the *employees' view* and the *company's view*. Based on these insights, the leadership styles and traits most suitable for agile and increasingly digitized organizational contexts are identified and discussed according to the responses of the organizations involved in the study.

Of course, the insights collected and discussed in this report are not exhaustive and cannot be generalized. However, they offer valuable insights for identifying some trends, challenges and opportunities and delineating some interesting paths about good and bad practices on leadership traits required in remote working organizational contexts, and even in not advanced economic systems with limited presence of companies like the Basilicata one.

2. Background

According to the need to understand and analyze how the dynamics of the remote and agile working influence and are, in turn, influenced by leadership styles, in the first report "*Mapping leadership characteristics - Analysis of the trends in leadership characteristics for organizations adopting remote working*" it was carried out an extensive analysis aimed to define the concept of "agile working", starting from the assumption that the notion of "agility" is traditionally related to the organizational capacity to identify new trends, opportunities and threats, to be fast, pro-active and resilient, to have change-ready mindset to keep moving, changing and adapting to the general and task environment in which it operates or could operate, mainly innovating business modelling, rethinking products and services to be addressed to actual and potential customers/users, revisiting operations, exploring the value of new resources and assets and defining a new platform of commercial and non-commercial relationships³.

It was also observed that this term partially coincided with the umbrella term of "remote working"⁴. Moreover, the concept of leadership was analysed, delineating it as a highly complex social process

³ On this concept, ZHELTOUKHOVA, K. *HR: Getting Smart About Agile Working*, London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development, CIPD, 2014.

⁴ On this concept, BEDNAR, P.M., WELCH, C. Bednar, P.M. *Socio-Technical Perspectives on Smart Working: Creating Meaningful and Sustainable Systems*. *Information Systems Frontiers*, 22, pp. 281-298, 2020; BOORSMA, B., MITCHELL, S. *Work-life innovation smart work – A paradigm shift transforming how, where, and when work gets done*, CISCO IBSG Point of View, PDF Report, 2011; LAKE, A. *Smart Flexibility: Moving smart and flexible working from theory to practice*, Burlington: Routledge, 2013; MC-EWAN, A.M., *Smart Working: Creating the Next Wave*, London and New York: Routledge, 2016.

of influencing a group toward the achievement of goals and directing the organization to make it more cohesive and coherent by applying specific values, beliefs, technical and emotional knowledge, experiences and culture⁵.

Specifically, the different forms of remote working were classified and analyzed both in terms of disadvantages⁶ and advantages⁷ from the workers' point of view and, equally, the disadvantages⁸ and the advantages⁹ from the organizational point of view. Then, trying to outline the fundamental traits of the concept of leadership¹⁰ considering frameworks and notions currently used¹¹ as, for example,

⁵ On this concept, BASS, B.M. *Does the Transactional-Transformational Leadership Paradigm Transcend Organizational and National Boundaries?*, *American Psychologist*, 52(2), pp. 130-139, 1997; DINIBUTUN, *Leadership: A Comprehensive Review of Literature*, Research and Theoretical Framework. *Journal of Economics and Business*, 3(1), pp. 44-64, 2020.

⁶ On this concept, MOSS, J. Moss, J. *Helping Remote Workers Avoid Loneliness and Burnout.*, *Harvard Business Review*, Available online at <https://hbr.org/2018/11/helping-remote-workers-avoid-loneliness-and-burnout> (last accessed: November 24, 2021), 2018; MARUYAMA, T., TIETZE, *From anxiety to assurance. Concerns and outcomes of telework.* *Person Rev.*, 41, pp.450-469, 2012; KRAUT, R.E. *Telecommuting: The Trade-Offs of Home Work*, *Journal of Communication*, 39(3), pp. 19-47, 1989; MOORE, J. *Homeworking and Work-Life Balance: Does It Add to Quality of Life?* *Revue Europeenne de Psychologie Appliquée*, 56(1), pp. 5-13, 2006; WOJCAK, E., BAJZIKOVA, L., SAJGALIKOVA, H., POLAKOVA, M. *How to achieve sustainable efficiency with teleworkers: Leadership model in telework.* *Proc. Soc. Behav. Sci.*, 229, pp. 33-41, 2016; GOLDEN, T.D., VEIGA, J.F., DINO, R.N. *The impact of professional isolation on teleworker job performance and turnover intentions: Does time spent teleworking, interacting face-to-face, or having access to communication-enhancing technology matter?*, *J. Applied Psychol.*, 93, p. 1412, doi 10.1037/a0012272, 2008; FEDAKOVA, D., ISTONOVA, I. *Slovak IT employess and new ways of working: impact on work-family borders and work-family balance*, *Ceskoslovenska Psychol.*, 61, pp. 68-83, 2017.

⁷ On this concept, FEDAKOVA, D., ISTONOVA, I. *Slovak IT employess and new ways of working: impact on work-family borders and work-family balance*, *Ceskoslovenska Psychol.*, 61, pp. 68-83, 2017; CHARALAMPOUS, M., GRANT, C.A., TRAMONTANO, C., MICHAILIDS, *Systematically reviewing remote e-workers' well-being at work: a multidimensional approach*, *European Journal of Work and Organizational psychology*, 28(1), pp. 51-73, 2020; HILL, E.J., GRZYWACZ, J.G., ALLEN, S., BLANCHARD, V.L., MATZ-COSTA, C., SHULKIN, S., PITT-CATSOUPHES, M. *Defining and Conceptualizing Workplace Flexibility*, *Community, Work and Family*, 11 (2), pp. 149-163, 2008;

⁸ VARMA, A., JAISWAI, A., PEREIRA, V., KUMAR, Y.L.N. *Leader-member exchange in the age of remote working*, *Human Resource Development International*, 25(2), pp. 219-230, 2022; CONTRERAS, F., BAVKAL, E., ABID, G. *E-leadership and teleworking in times of COVID-19 and beyond: What we Know and Where Do We Go*, *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, pp.1-11, 2020; STEUDE, D.H. *Challenges of Remote Leadership in a Digitalized Working World 4.0*, *Sciend*, doi.org/10.1515/mosr-2021-0005, 2021;

⁹ On this concept, NAKROSIEN, A., BUCIUNIENE, L., GOSATUTAITE, B. *Working from home: Characteristics and outcomes of telework.* *Int. J. Manpower*, 40, pp. 883-898, 2019; KLOPOTEK, M. *The advantages and disadvantages of remote working from the perspective of young employees*, *Organiz. Manage.*, 4, pp. 39-49, 2017; CORTELLAZZO, L., BRUNI, E., ZAMPIERI, R., *The role of leadership in a digitalized world: A review*, *Frontiers in psychology*, 10, 1938, 2019; GIOVANIS, E. *The relationships between teleworking, traffic and air pollution*, *Atmosphere Poll. Res.*, 9, pp. 1-14, 2018; MALHOTRA, A., MAJCHRZAK, A., ROSEN, B. *Leading virtual teams.* *Acad. Manage. Perspect.*, 21, pp. 60-70, 2007;

¹⁰ ZEUGE, A., Zeuge, A., Oschinsky, F., Weigel, A., Schlechtinger, M., Niehaves, B. (2020). *Leading Virtual Teams-A Literature Review*. Von <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/uploads/prod/2020/07/NFW-Zeuge-et-al.pdf> am, 3, 2020.

¹¹ On this concept, AVOLIO, B.J., SOSIK, J.J., KAHAI, S.S., BAKER, B. Avolio, B. J., Sosik, J. J., Kahai, S. S., Baker, B. *E-leadership: Re-examining transformations in leadership source and transmission*, *The Leadership Quarterly*, 25(1), pp. 105-131, 2014; VAN WART, M., ROMAN, A., WANG, X., LIU, C. *Operationalizing the definition of e-leadership: identifying the elements of e-leadership*, *International review of administrative sciences*, 85(1), pp. 80-97, 2019; COUN, M.J.H., EDELBROEK, R., PETERS, P., BLOMME, R.J. *Leading Innovative Work-Behavior in Times of COVID-19: Relationship Between Leadership Style, Innovative Work-Behavior, Work-Related Flow, and IT-Enabled Presence Awareness During the First and Second Wave of the COVID-19 Pandemic*, *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, pp. 1-16, 2021; TERKAMO-MOISIO, A., KARKI, S., KANGASNIEMI, M., LAMMINTAKANEN, J., HAGGMAN-LAITILA, A. *Towards Remote Leadership in Health Care: Lessons Learned from an Integrative Review*, *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 78 (3), pp. 595-608, 2022; HARRIS, A., DE FLAMINIS, *Distributed Leadership in Practice: Evidence, Misconceptions*

e-leadership¹² - different types of leadership styles were delineated according to some archetypes labelled Directive Leadership, Catalyst Leadership, Resonant Leadership, Servant Leadership, Transformational Leadership, Authentic Leadership, E-Leadership/Leadership 4.0, Distributed Leadership, Shared Leadership. These styles are summarized in the following table.

Leadership style	Main characteristics
Directive Leadership	Ability to organise and manage work, defining the roles of each employee. Power to exercise control over the initiating structure model.
Catalyst Leadership	Ability to lead change by involving Human Resource, creating a climate of trust and participation.
Resonant Leadership	Ability to spread enthusiasm and trust. It is intended as a real contagion of emotions.
Servant Leadership	Ability to influence others by acting as a guide, with the aim of promoting team success rather than personal success, taking into account the employee's well-being and creating a relationship of mutual trust with human resources.
Transformational Leadership	Ability to encourage human resources to achieve company objectives, in an agile work context.
Authentic Leadership	Creating authentic and sincere relationships with the group.
E-leadership / Leadership 4.0	Ability to guide human resources using technological supports.
Distributed Leadership	Possession of direction and management skills.
Shared Leadership	Ability to fully share one's role as leader, one's powers, and one's commitments, with the teams.

Table 1. Styles of leadership concerning remote or agile working environments and their main characteristics¹³

The literature review, as described in the previous report, allowed us to identify some main characteristics of a leader in a remote/agile working environment. Leaders should possess emotional intelligence, which encompasses trust, empathy, and humanity. This helps in building strong relationships and understanding the needs of team members. They should be able to build strong relationships, understand the needs of team members, inspire and motivate their employees, build and plan future activities and organizational strategies always keeping the teams' attention at the forefront. Leaders should also prioritize the team and share leadership roles and powers, creating a collaborative and participatory environment. Furthermore, the leader in a remote/agile working environment should have the following attributes: vision, inspiration, self-awareness, ability to create relationships, aptitude for continuous learning, ability to perform tasks, innovation, and ethics.

and Possibilities, *Journal of Management Education*, 30(4), pp. 141–146, 2016; IANNOTTA, M., MERET, C., MARCHETTI, G. *Defining Leadership in Smart Working Contexts: A Concept Synthesis*, *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, pp. 1–11, 2020; TANDON, A. *Leading Learning and Innovation in Organizations: A Distributed Leadership Perspective*, *Development and Learning in Organizations: An International Journal*, 36(2), pp. 5–7, 2021.

¹² CONTRERAS, F., BAYKACL, E., ABID, G. *E-leadership and teleworking in times of COVID-19 and beyond: What we Know and Where Do We Go*, *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, pp.1-11, 2020.

¹³ PONTILLO, S., DI LAURO, S., ANTONELLI, G., *Defining the Leader in an Agile and Remote Working Environment*, *PuntOorg International Journal*, vol. 7(2), p. 160, 2022.

Considering the leadership styles and characteristics required of leaders in a remote working environment, this second year of research aimed to explore how leaders operate in remote working environments and what competencies they develop and exercise within companies operating in the Basilicata region.

The underlying idea is to understand the leadership styles and best practices that managers and entrepreneurs employ to navigate an organizational transformation.

To this end, a qualitative field research was conducted to identify best practices on leadership characteristics supporting the remote working philosophy. Consistently with the project's objectives, the research, whose methodological aspects and results are described below, involved several companies in Basilicata that systematically implement remote working.

PART I – Empirical analysis

3. Overview

To explore how the theoretical framework and concepts presented in the first report are applied in practice, it is particularly insightful to examine first the evolving dynamics of remote work in the Italian context post-COVID-19 pandemic.

Where the engine triggering a massive adoption of a dynamic such as remote working unquestionably remains the pandemic phenomenon¹⁴, it must be underlined that such a form of non-in-person work existed before this catalysing event.

In fact, it already existed the resolution of the European Parliament of 13 September 2016, which argued about the need of *"creating labor market conditions favorable to private life balance and professional life"*¹⁵. Additionally, within the Italian national context, there existed the law number 81 dated 22 May 2017 aimed at *"promoting flexible articulation in the times and places of subordinate work"*¹⁶.

A similar regulatory determination highlights how a similar form of work was already adopted in some cases and some specific ways, and in parallel with the launch and massive development of the

Internet. If we look at the US context, for example, the legislation seems significantly ahead of the Italian one: a stimulus to the adoption of forms of remote working began with the Clean Air Act of 1990, and the concept itself was born even earlier, under the name of telecommuting, by the American physicist Jack Nilles, the first to coin the term in 1973 and to standardize a definition in 1994 in the sense of *"the substitution of telecommunications and/or computers for commuting work"*¹⁷.

The idea of a delocalization from the primary places of work and of a focus centred on the use of technological tools to carry out work activities remotely was consolidated in the literature in the following years, enriching Nilles' definition and understanding the newborn smart working alias agile working as *"an alternative work arrangement in which employees perform tasks elsewhere that are*

¹⁴ BERTOLINI, S., FULLIN, G., GOGLIO, V., PACETTI, *Il lavoro da remoto alla prova dell'emergenza. Implicazioni sociali e organizzative*, Cambio. Rivista sulle trasformazioni sociali, 11 (22), pp. 69-82, 2021.

¹⁵ Risoluzione del Parlamento europeo del 13 settembre 2016 sulla creazione di condizioni del mercato del lavoro favorevoli all'equilibrio tra vita privata e vita professionale, www.europarl.europa.eu.

¹⁶ LEGGE 22 maggio 2017, n. 81. www.gazzettaufficiale.it.

¹⁷ NILLES, J.M. *Making Telecommuting Happen: A Guide for Telemanagers and Telecommuters*, Van Nostrand Reinhold, 1994.

normally done in a primary or central workplace, for at least some portion of their work schedule, using electronic media to interact with others inside and outside the organisation”¹⁸.

Regarding the Italian context, a report elaborated by Assolombarda of 2022 - in turn referring to Eurostat data - states that in Italy in 2022 the percentage of employed people between 15 and 64 years of age who carry out their work occasionally or habitually from home is equal to 12.2% (corresponding to 2,734 million workers), positioning Italy in the last places among the 27 EU countries and lower than the European average of 22.4%. However, the share of remote workers has increased significantly compared to the 4.6% of the pre-pandemic period (2019 average), even if decreasing compared to the peaks of 2020 (13.6%) and 2021 (14.8%). In this vein, the Smart Working Observatory of the Polytechnic of Milan estimated a diffusion rate (i.e. the percentage of companies that have introduced smart working) in the private sector of 48% in SMEs (10-250 employees). This percentage reaches 91% in large companies (over 250 employees) and stands at 67% in public administration”¹⁹. More recently, the same Observatory underlined how in 2023 remote workers in Italy were around 3.585 million, a slight increase compared to the 3.570 million in 2022, but a good 541% more than pre-Covid. In 2024, projections identify 3.65 million smart workers in Italy.

During 2023, remote workers grew in particular in large companies, with more than half workforce operating in agile mode. However, they continued to decline in micro-enterprises (about 9% of the total workforce) and Public Administrations (about 16% of the total workforce). It emerges also that almost all large companies (96%) include smart working initiatives, largely with structured models, with 20% of companies committed to extending the application to technical and operational profiles previously excluded.

Smart working is also applied in 56% of SMEs, where it is usually applied with informal models often managed at the level of specific teams, and in 61% of the public bodies, with structured initiatives implemented especially in larger entities. Comparing these data with the data of the Eurozone, it emerges a scenario in which Italy still shows a backward position compared to other European nations. The same Eurostat data also underline how in 2023 only 4.4% of Italian workers worked in smart working for more than half of their weekly hours, with percentages not too dissimilar to Slovakia (4.9%) and Cyprus (3.8%) and with a notable gap compared to the leading smart countries, such as Finland (22.4%) and a Eurozone average of 9%²⁰.

4. Context of analysis

In line with the objectives of the NODES Smart West project, the findings and insights from the desk analysis have been examined and tested within a specific regional context, namely Basilicata, one of the southern regions involved in the project.

In particular, it was questioned if and how the companies with headquarters in Basilicata or mainly operating in Basilicata interpret and apply remote working practices and how leadership styles affect and reflect this *modus operandi*.

To provide value and significance to the empirical analysis, it is fundamental to summarize some key socio-economic features characterizing the Basilicata regional system. Specifically:

- the region is configured as small in size, especially from a demographic point of view, with a population as of 1 January 2024 of 533.636 inhabitants²¹, distributed in morphologically diversified

¹⁸ GAJENDRAN, R.S., HARRISON, D.A. *The good, the bad, and the unknown about telecommuting: Meta-analysis of psychological mediators and individual consequences*, Journal of Applied Psychology, 92(6), 1524–1541, 2007.

¹⁹ “Lo smart working in numeri. Anno 2022. Rapporto numero 05/2023. Area centro studi”. www.assolombarda.it

²⁰ CALABRESE, E. “Lavoro agile, Italia tra le ultime in classifica nei Paesi Ue per smart working riconosciuto ai lavoratori”, www.ilsole24ore.com, 2024

²¹ “Popolazione residente al 1 Gennaio: Basilicata”, www.dat.istat.it

areas with a plethora of small villages and very limited cities acting as economic and social hubs for the whole region;

- as of 2023, it had 36.675 active companies, 1470 SMEs, 620 foreign trade operators, with a GDP of 14 billion and 969 million euros, an export weight equal to 18.9% of GDP, with 44% of the latter aimed at non-EU countries²². The change in GDP between 2022 and 2023 coincides with the national average (+0.9%)²³;

- the region presents 5.8% of GDP belonging to the primary sector (agriculture, forestry and fishing), 31% to industry (and specifically 24.9% to industry in the strict sense and 6.1% to construction), and 63.2% to services, mainly related to PA bodies²⁴.

5. Data and methods

The empirical analysis was developed according to three main stages. The *first stage* was aimed at identifying the companies and the organizations to be potentially involved in the study. For operative purposes, it was divided into *three macro-activities*.

The *first macro-activity* involved a scoping desk analysis using different sources mainly web-based to collect preliminary inputs and suggestions regarding industries, companies and organizations based in Basilicata and applying remote working practices. Unfortunately, this activity revealed the limited use of remote working.

The *second macro-activity* was related to the contact and the engagement of experts and leaders of the local business and managerial world, and relevant actors and stakeholders such as Confindustria Basilicata and Federmanager Basilicata. These interactions confirmed the concerns about the identification of suitable companies and organizations to participate in the study due to the region's

specific gaps, including a generally low availability and use of technological and digital tools, a very limited number of companies with robust organizational structures and an explicit need for remote working practices, and little attention to HRM, to name a few of the most commonly cited issues.

Matching the results and the insights derived from the first macro-activity with the very useful suggestions gathered in the second macro-activity through the interactions with the local experts and the stakeholders, it was possible to elaborate, as *third macro-activity*, consisting in delineating a preliminary list of companies and organizations based in or mainly operating in Basilicata that could potentially be considered and contacted for the ongoing empirical study.

In the *second stage* of the empirical investigation, the companies and the organisations identified in the preliminary list were contacted by mail and phone. All of them responded positively to the information asked and were open to engaging with the research team. Following this initial contact, the list was revised and refined to include only those companies that were structurally implementing remote working practices. As hypothesized, these companies were all operating in industries related to ICT products and services.

Finally, in the *third stage* of the empirical investigation, the five companies selected were contacted again to schedule specific dates, times, and modalities for submitting and sharing the questionnaire that had been developed for this purpose and to have direct interviews virtually or on-site, aimed to explore and capture additional thoughts and qualitative comments from the questionnaire's respondents. The questionnaire was structured into two main sections: the first section gathered

²² "Basilicata", www.sace.it

²³ "Pil Basilicata, bassa la crescita nel 2023: +0.9%", www.rainews.it

²⁴ "L'economia della Basilicata – rapporto annuale" (2023), www.bancaditalia.it

significant information for company profiling, while the second section focused on understanding the modalities and impact of remote working practices within the organizations, as well as the related leadership styles and practices adopted by entrepreneurs, CEOs, and top managers. The details of the companies' profiles – labelled anonymously using greek letters for privacy purposes - and the insights derived from the empirical investigation are summarized in the following sections.

PART II – Case studies

6. Alfa

The company *Alfa s.r.l.* is a limited liability company based in Matera, classified under the Ateco code 6202, which encompasses companies engaged in "*consultancy in the technology sector of information*". From an accounting perspective, the company reported a turnover of over one million two hundred thousand euros in 2022, along with a profit of 38,442 euros for the same year, net of a resulting share capital of 10,000 euros in 2024. The company had 33 active employees during the same year.

Founded in 2010, *Alfa* is a software house specializing in offering software products and services based on advanced technologies. Leveraging its accumulated expertise, the company has developed a deep know-how in all phases of the software life cycle, including design, maintenance, and support. The company's expansion, and the opening to markets outside the strictly local one (as of 2020, the main geographical areas of reference for company demand were central-northern Italy and the United States of America, also through partnerships with big companies such as Team System, Lottomatica - crucial for the birth of relationships with the North American continent, Samsung Italia, Txt and Unicredit) have resulted in a tripled turnover in the 2015-2020 window and the stabilization of the general team numbering over 30 units, with an average age of around 30 years.

The company supply/demand is both B2B and B2C. As of 2024, the average length of employment is 4.1 years.

A significant factor in the company's growth has been the spin-off *Alfa Iot s.r.l.*, derived from *Alfa* in 2026, with the aim of "*developing innovative IT products with high technological value*". The spin-off company was then registered in Boston in the USA in 2017. Subsequently, the X industrial group entered the company - to change the business model - contributing to a turnover of over 77 million euros. X is a leading company in the aluminium surface treatment sector, having been founded in 1941.

The company strategy still aims to attract talented individuals, especially young ones, operating in the tech sector. The primary goal is to identify those who have established themselves professionally in companies in northern Italy and allow them to start a professional path in a geographical horizon closer to the land of origin.

The company's areas of specialization within the IT landscape are diverse and are summarized on the company's website in the following categories:

- 1) AI consultancy, with support services in the integration of advanced AI solutions for process optimization (predictive analysis, virtual assistance and advanced chatbots, automation of business processes, querying of company data, analysis and classification of documents, automatic generation of reports and documents, processing and analysis of images and videos, generation of prototypes and automatic design, generation of creative and personalized content, assisted training, translation tools and generation of multilingual content, sentiment analysis);

- 2) IOT (Internet of Things) and automation solutions, through the creation of integrated systems of devices, cloud data and sensors;
- 3) Support for businesses in the transition towards the Smart Factory and Industry 5.0;
- 4) Telemedicine Software;
- 5) Mobile application development;
- 6) Offer of products such as 3D configurators, commodo, palletizer, XBUS, Tessil-e;
- 7) R&D especially through participation in the SmartFactory – One Vision project, a ministerial initiative addressing the issues of *"evolutionary and adaptive production systems for personalized production"*: The project aims to design and prototype an integrated platform capable of optimizing the time and costs of industrial production through advanced Business Intelligence techniques and the use of IoT technology."

Regarding the specific objectives of the NODES Smart West project, the company was open to answering the questionnaire and participating in a direct in-person interview with the research team. Initially, it was emphasized that the company is in a transitional phase, with a need to focus its efforts on improving the quality of its projects and elevating their level. The company desires to concentrate on more relevant projects, ideally linked to the Internet of Things (IoT), moving beyond mature products and services such as ERP software.

These objectives are being addressed within a corporate context where remote work has been a structural practice since 2020, initially as a constraint imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic and subsequently as a regular working practice. Currently, the entire workforce is engaged in remote work, although this is implemented based on internal turnover criteria: 25% of workers (8/36) are on remote work daily, while the entire workforce works remotely on Fridays. Additionally, some employees have the flexibility to work remotely throughout the week, depending on organizational needs.

From the interview, it emerged that in a cost-benefit analysis from the workers' perspective, the main undoubted benefits are linked to a greater work-life balance and reduced commuting times. On the other hand, remote work increases isolation and feelings of loneliness, sometimes leading to technostress. To mitigate the feelings of stagnation and isolation that can arise in the long term from a working method that risks becoming a constant (referred to as "the mechanism of mental abandonment"), the company management has introduced a series of specific actions, such as *'the introduction of the unexpected'*, i.e. the voluntary introduction of an element breaking the employee's working routine to implement a more vivid connection with the surrounding reality and the collaborators in distance.

From a company and ownership perspective, the benefits of remote work primarily concern reduced absenteeism rates and greater ease in finding personnel with adequate know-how compared to competing companies that adhere to the 'dogma' of physical headquarters. In terms of disadvantages, while physical distance may inhibit conflicts, making their management less necessary, there are concerns about creating and consolidating a common corporate culture and organizational values among remote working employees, especially among those recently hired, seldom enjoying the physical spaces and colleagues in presence.

Investigating the relationship between leadership styles and remote working practices adopted at *Alfa*, the three main qualities shaping the 'remote' leader are identified as coaching, adaptability, and adequate communication skills. The latter is particularly essential in a context where communication takes on greater importance compared to traditional working methods and where shared leadership practices, partially distributing the burden of company management, do not take place.

Compared to the different leadership styles formalized in the table mentioned in the report, the overall leadership style adopted by the company management encompasses and integrates almost all the characteristics of the theoretically delineated leadership styles. What seems functional for effective leadership is to maintain a constant check on the situation of remote working employees, and, above all, to differentiate and often personalize the leadership style based on individual characteristics, levels of anxiety and stress, ability to respect deadlines and tasks, attitudes, and recurring behaviours also considering the potential different situations lived, for example, by male and female employees. Regarding the potential evolution of remote working practices at *Alfa* in the coming years, there is a need to build and enhance new aggregative HR dynamics aimed at supporting a continuous improvement in the quality of life of employees, thus partially counterbalancing the negative elements found in the current application of remote working practices.

7. Beta

Founded in 2000, *Beta* represents one of the main, and longest-standing, existing realities in the Lucanian ICT sector. The company is "*specialized in the design, creation and management of solutions for the electronic archiving and processing of documents. It integrates operational management, technologies and process management to design and implement, in all sectors, advanced and complete Business Process Outsourcing solutions*". Its mission, as exemplified on the company website, is to "*offer cutting-edge solutions with regards to technologies and methodologies both in the acquisition, processing and conservation phase of documents and in that of distribution of documents via electronic network << dematerialized >>*" while its vision is

“creating a smart environment to facilitate and simplify people's lives. Together we generate efficiency and innovation for our customers by creating, in the community and in the territory, economic value, individual opportunities and business culture”. Currently, the company is configured as a corporate structure of a joint stock company and has its main headquarter in Basilicata, in Sant’Angelo Le Fratte, near the city of Potenza. It operates through eight plants, whose five are based in Basilicata, and counts over 1.000 employees. The company appears to be at the forefront in terms of its working model and the services offered to its employees, as evidenced by the longstanding presence of an internal company nursery for the children of both male and female workers, which has contributed to the full consolidation of a remote working dynamic.

An important change in the entire corporate structure of *Beta* took place in 2021 when, during the COVID-19 pandemic, 70% of *Beta* and 100% of the subsidiaries Y and K were acquired by the Spanish company J, in turn, controlled by Z, a Spanish multinational listed on the stock exchange and operating in the IT sector, with a turnover of over 4.34 billion euros in 2023. The objective of the acquisition, by J, is to penetrate the Italian markets through the forecasting of the growth of *Beta*, whose acquisition leads to a sum of work units equal to over 2200 employees. The last years – under the Spanish management - are characterized by the development of new partnerships, especially with "*an important banking player, as well as two leading companies in Italian large-scale distribution and a primary operator in telecommunications services*".

To date, *Beta* alone has a turnover of over 24 million euros and the composition of its employees is characterized by a 67% female presence, of 55% of graduates with an average age of less than 40 years. In this context, it's also crucial to highlight the company's commitment to social policies, including gender equality, based on the SA8000:2014 standard for Social Accountability and the reference practice UNI/PdR 125:2022 for gender equality. This commitment is reflected in the adoption of practices aimed at "*the use of an inclusive language in communications, the access and*

career development model based on meritocratic and non-discriminatory criteria, training on diversity & inclusion issues, the services to support the parenting, and measures that facilitate conciliation, among which stands out a smart working model, which has been operational for years, which guarantees flexibility and work-home conciliation". At the industrial level, the company value proposition is focused on the offering of:

1. Business Process Outsourcing (BPO): Taking charge, as an external supplier, of optimizing, controlling, and managing entire business processes to reduce operating costs, focus time and resources on core processes, continuously improve efficiency and effectiveness, enhance services and customer satisfaction, and increase overall organizational flexibility;
2. Document and Content Management: Managing and storing data and resulting company information;
3. Creating Solutions: Developing solutions that enable client organizations to simplify their operational processes and optimize the use of human capital by automating repetitive activities with low added value or high risks of operational errors, thus improving those with higher added value, with the assistance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Robotic Process Automation techniques;
4. Distance Learning Activities: Designing and implementing online courses based on a customized platform.

Regarding the specific issues under investigation, through the administration of the questionnaire and an online interview, it emerged that *Beta* has adopted remote working practices since 2019. These practices were significantly consolidated and standardized during the COVID-19 pandemic, leading to the current situation where 66% (approximately 1,200 employees) of the overall workforce works remotely regularly.

The adoption of remote working practices seems to guarantee different benefits such as *i*) the contribution to the organizational commitment, *ii*) the reduction of the rate of absenteeism, *iii*) the improvement of the process of standardization of the procedures, *iv*) the improvement of the corporate reputation, *v*) the possibility of easily recruiting specialized personnel without limitations due to the geographical positioning of the working spaces of the company.

The minimal critical issues related to the adoption of remote working practices primarily concern the potential difficulties in monitoring and supporting remote workers and the risks to the company's IT security. While there is greater difficulty in managing teamwork and reinforcing organizational culture and values, specific concerns arise about conflict management, which becomes more challenging to resolve remotely.

Among the critical elements that employees are facing with the adoption of remote working practices, there is an increase in isolation and loneliness, which contrasts with the main benefit of increased work performance.

Consistent with this, and in a broad verticalized context, the most crucial skill of leaders appears to be the mastery of adequate communication skills, especially regarding the resolution of problems arising from physical distance. This leadership style most closely aligns with Catalyst Leadership, characterized by the ability to guide change through the creation of a climate of trust, a feeling inevitably rooted in effective communication.

Regarding the future of remote work, it is considered an essential managerial element that can enhance effective recruitment and related reward mechanisms, ultimately ensuring greater employee gratification and achievement of corporate business objectives.

8. Gamma

Gamma is one of the oldest companies in the IT sector in Basilicata. The company currently presents itself in the form of a joint-stock company and has the ATECO code 6201, indicating an activity of "production of software not connected to the edition". The company locates its headquarter in Tito, in the province of Potenza. As of the latest available data, *Gamma* achieved a turnover of €7,328,044.00 in 2022, with a corresponding profit of €507,678.00, a share capital of €1,600,000.00 as of 2024, and employs 89 people.

Originally founded as W Computer in 1982 as a system house, i.e. a provider of comprehensive IT services, including hardware and software, often acting as an intermediary between producers and end customers, the company's development has been driven by a value proposition focused on "*Develop and provide Information & Communication Technology solutions and services to the Public Administration through research, consultancy and outsourcing*".

Between 1985 and 1991, the company experienced growth, specializing in the creation and design of IT systems for public administration. On April 7, 1989, the company was formally registered as *Gamma S.p.A.* In 2006, *Gamma* became part of the CREATEC consortium, which includes various Lucanian companies operating in the environmental and technological innovation sectors. The following years were then characterized by a further expansion of activities: in 2007, the company

entered the research sector, participating in national projects. From 2010 to 2016, *Gamma* consolidated its presence in central and southern Italy, assuming a leadership position in the local public administration market. This expansion led to the opening of a new headquarters in Salerno and the development of a software factory in Telesse Terme, in the province of Benevento.

The company offers a varied portfolio of solutions and services. The solutions are configured as "*tools integrated with national enabling platforms and designed following the guidelines drawn up by AgID and the Digital Transformation Team*" according to four main lines of development, such as the Local Authority Digital System, Document Management, HR Management and Digital

Platforms for E-government. On the other side, the services can be usefully grouped in four main lines, such as:

1. Consulting & Training, to intervene "*in the analysis, (re)design and management of administrative processes and document flows, in order to guide the organization towards complete digitalisation and simplification of procedures*";
2. Outsourcing, i.e. integrated support in the governance of administrations;
3. System Integration & Management, and therefore the provision of "*technical, systems and continuity assistance services, guaranteeing both remote and on-site management and monitoring of IT systems*" (Disaster Recovery and Business Continuity services; assistance in the field of Security and Intrusion Prevention; virtualization services; design and creation of Linux network infrastructures; implementation of backup and disaster recovery projects in the Cloud);
4. Assistance, through a multi-channel customer care agent service.

The company's target audience primarily consists of local authorities, regional offices, the national health system, companies involved in public utility services, and the central public administration. According to insights gained from both the questionnaire administration and online interviews with *Gamma S.p.a.*'s CEO, remote work practices were initially implemented in response to the COVID-

19 pandemic. This unstructured approach aimed to adapt the company to the 'stay-at-home' paradigm. Given *Gamma's* status as an ICT company, this forced experiment proved particularly successful. Employees demonstrated their ability to collaborate effectively, even when physically separated. Positive results were then observed, in terms of improvement in productivity, reduction of commuting times from home to office, a more flexible distribution of the working hours increasingly objectives-oriented.

As COVID-19 waned, people asked to return to office but there was a lot of resistance and even cases of dumping by other companies (including big tech companies of the calibre of Google and Microsoft) that promised full smart working.

Consequently, remote work was institutionalized and included in employment contracts. To prevent companies from exploiting this trend and losing talent, measures were implemented. This approach attracted skilled workers from regions like Campania, Puglia, Sicily, and southern Lazio, fostering positive workforce mobility that likely wouldn't have occurred if traditional in-person work requirements were strictly enforced in Basilicata.

However, to manage a smooth transition towards diffuse remote working practices project managers are still present in the company twice a week, equally allowing for double channel in person and remotely (typically via Google Meet) for meetings. Currently, 90% of employees work remotely, and practically all the processes take place online based on a complete re-engineering of

the main business activities, such as reporting, ticket requests, administration and secretarial services. Regarding the adoption of remote working practices in *Gamma*, in terms of advantages and disadvantages for the organization, it was highlighted that there has been an increase in the process of standardization of procedures. This led to a significant overall reduction in both fixed and variable costs. In response, the company's consultants adopted a dual pricing structure, with different rates depending on whether the consultancy is conducted in person or remotely. A further advantage of remote work practices, as previously mentioned, was the ease of recruiting personnel.

Additionally, the company's reputation improved, not only among customers but also among employees.

The relatively negative sides of remote working are identified in *i)* a negative impact on the corporate culture and values, *ii)* the longer times of the training of the new people recruited and *iii)* teamwork management. To address these challenges, the company has designated specific days called 'Start Days' and established an association called CUBE. This association organizes events such as parties, farm visits on Sundays, and similar events to foster connections and break down the barriers and negative mindsets associated with physical distance.

It also emerged that employee evaluations have become more meritocratic, as they are now based on a quantitative and qualitative parametric model, not influenced by direct personal relationships and managers' perceptions. What acquires greater relevance, then, are the groups, the teams and the team leader. This latter becomes a central point of the process of the organization and management of the remote working employees and teams with bi-monthly interviews conducted to discuss work progress while also addressing the human elements of collaboration. According to this view, the leadership style adopted by the company can be identified as a mix of the three styles of catalyst leadership, servant leadership and transformational leadership.

9. Delta

The *Delta* company deals, as per Ateco code 62.01, with the "production of software not connected to the edition". It is based in Matera and is configured in the corporate structure of a joint-stock

company (S.P.A.). Its turnover, as of 2022, amounted to €5,704,176.00, while its profit for the same year amounted to €766,212.00. Compared to the year 2024, however, its share capital is one million euros, and the number of employees currently employed by the company is equal to 29 units.

The company represents a thriving Lucanian company operating in the ICT sector, since 2001. The foundation of the company falls within the framework of the ESA project (The European Space Agency) called COSMO-SkyMed (Constellation of small Satellites for the Mediterranean Basin Observation), with the role of algorithmic developer for the first dual system (military and civil) of earth observation radar satellites.

From 2002 to 2009, the company's know-how grows, and in parallel with the latter the ability to develop algorithms and processing of SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) data: in these years the company broadens the horizon of its partnerships, establishing links with companies and organizations such as Finmeccanica/Leonardo, Thales Alenia Space and consolidating its links with the Italian Space Agency and the European Space Agency. This growth process reached a new turning point in 2010, with the acquisition of the company Exent s.r.l., also operating in the ICT sector, and through which *Delta* can expand its customer portfolio to SMEs and public administration. This step represents a further element in the growth and diversification process, in

the acquisition of other companies, in the expansion of national and international partnerships, so much so that in 2015, the company received recognition as an "innovative company" from the Ministry of Economic Development, included in the list of the 500 Italian companies relevant for skills and active contribution to the diffusion of technological innovation. In 2017, the company changed its legal configuration, taking on the formal characteristics of a joint-stock company, and launching a particularly important partnership with TIM in the R&D field to encourage 5G experimentation. In 2021 the company reaches the status of European Digital Innovation Hub, i.e. a structure that provides assistance and support to both public and private organizations in responding to the challenges of digitalisation and increasing their competitiveness.

Concerning the services offered by the organization, they are particularly wide. The main IT services offered can be identified, as per the company website, in software solutions, private cloud, remote working services, virtual servers, Unified Communication applications, Data Base and security, also through the help of numerous certified partners. These services are expressed in specific technical solutions, such as the supply of Managed Service Provider packages, Managed Security Service Provider, e-mail and certified e-mail, hosting, purchase and renewal of domains, domain certification, help desk, housing of customer-owned machines, creation of websites/e-commerce, GDPR platform and auditing services for verifying regulatory compliance, Bitrix24 CRM and cybersecurity services.

The company also boasts strong experience in the R&D sector, and especially in the aerospace sector, with the possible supply of customized solutions regarding the design, development, integration and validation of the Ground Segment of space missions, prototyping, development and engineering of software for data management (optical, radar, etc.) and for post-processing (geocoding, data mosaicking, etc.), design and development of software systems for environmental monitoring, design and development of software systems for IoT and Smart Cities, design of software platforms for business 4.0.

When interviewed about the costs, benefits, and impacts of remote working practices, *Delta* seems to not share completely the common techno-optimistic views. The company perceives remote working more as an imposition determined by the spirit of the times rather than as a desirable or beneficial element for its vision and growth. The history of the adoption of remote working practices in the company begins with the COVID-19 pandemic.

Subsequently, during the transition from the pandemic to a return to normality, a hybrid approach was implemented, alternating between remote and in-person work, followed by a return to the company's spaces for all the staff. It should be underlined that this return, perceived as an imposition, has led to an increase in work proposals from other companies to its employees, making it challenging to manage staff turnover. To solve these emerging concerns, the company moved towards a more structured practice of remote working. However, the creation and management of the dedicated team did not work effectively.

A hybrid model was therefore chosen and is currently used. This model establishes that employees living within 60 km of the company go weekly for two days in presence and three days staying at home in smart, while those living beyond this distance work entirely remotely. This has inevitably facilitated the possibility of recruiting high-skilled professionals outside the regular geographical area of origin, resulting in a workforce that is not only spread across the Lucanian region but also includes employees in Rome, Milan, and, with an international presence, Albania.

In such a corporate context, a hybrid interaction event has been created for all the collaborators of the organization. During these events, direct interactions take place between the parties both in person and via video conference to discuss work progress and any problems emerging, to create a shared corporate culture and to reinforce organizational values.

This meeting proved to be particularly important, especially for the members who joined the company from scratch and have always operated in the full smart formula. In terms of advantages and disadvantages related to remote working practices, the company identified significant savings in terms of commuting time and transportation costs as well as the possibility of a better balance between the professional and private spheres for employees. However, remote work was also seen as potentially alienating, with technostress and increased negative feelings linked to loneliness and a sense of isolation.

Beyond the corporate advantages and disadvantages, the benefits for the company are limited. The possibility of finding specialized personnel without geographical constraints and an increase in employees' "loyalty" are considered the more relevant benefits, while no great advantages emerge related to energy consumption and the standardization of procedures, which were already implemented. Remote work practices are seen also as creator of negative impact on organizational values and culture. To overcome these concerns, different initiatives have been recently elaborated, such as weekend family residential formulas in Matera for employees working always remotely.

No direct evidence emerged regarding leadership skills related to the adoption of remote working practices, since the growth of the company and the process of creating a structured and formal organization able to address, manage and check remote working practices is still ongoing. However, the communication skills of the leaders are identified as the main levers for mitigating the communication challenges arising from this organizational restructuring.

To address this need, an HR direction was recently created recruiting two new resources specifically dedicated to HR management.

Regarding the future evolution of remote working, it is perceived as inevitable and the related process as irreversible. Nonetheless, it was highlighted that, while it is true that a reduction in remote work might be perceived negatively, it is equally important to keep moments of real face-to-face contact among people.

10. Theta

The *Theta* company is a limited liability company (s.r.l.) founded in 2001 in Matera, with operational offices also in Potenza, Bari and Milano. The organization's ateco code is 82.1, indicating "support activities for office functions". The company's core business is focused on the outsourced contact

centre sector (i.e. the delegation of call centre activities by a company to a specifically dedicated external organisation) and market research. The company has achieved a prominent position among sector players at the national and international levels offering the following services:

1. Inbound contact centre, and therefore offering customer care and CRM services, multilingual help desk, order collection and management, pre-and post-sales assistance, booking services and switchboard management;
2. Outbound contact centre, and therefore offering telemarketing services, telesales, database re-development, appointment diary management, push email/SMS campaigns and automatic call processor campaigns;
3. Qualitative market research, through the management of focus groups, and in-depth interviews, which cover fields of application such as positioning analysis and benchmarking,
4. campaign validation (pre-post), notoriety, knowledge, brand awareness, name tests, brand image, concept test/product test, packaging test, analysis of incentive systems and loyalty mechanisms and analysis of the customer base;
5. Quantitative market research, through telephone interviews supported by the C.A.T.I. system. (Computer Aided Telephone Interview) and face-to-face interviews supported by the C.A.P.I. system. (Computer Aided Personal Interview), applied to sectors such as Politics, Fairs/demonstrations/events, Public transport, Public utilities, Social investigations, Large-scale retail trade, Public Administration, Communication and advertising, Publishing and media; the main quantitative research products offered by the company are customer satisfaction, opinion polls, political polls, corporate and brand positioning, corporate and brand awareness, campaign validation and satisfaction with promotions and initiatives.

Based on the interview held with the CEO and the HR manager, it emerges that the company adopted remote working practices till 2017 as an initiative of internal welfare to address the specific needs of some categories of workers, in particular mothers with babies, disabled people, workers coming from small countries and villages experiencing difficulties with local transports and commuting issues. Remote working determined a better balance between working and private life, benefits regarding time management and cost savings related to mobility, improvement of performances and organizational climate.

During the COVID-19 pandemic and with the return to the working “normality”, remote working – with internal practicalities related to the need to guarantee the presence of a percentage of workers operating in the corporate offices - has been adopted for all workers. Surprisingly, for a rather long time, these practices have determined only advantages and benefits both for employees and the company, particularly in terms of performance, productivity, reduction of absenteeism and turnover, trust between employees and owners/top managers, company’s reputation and branding.

Currently, together with the different benefits gained through remote working by employees and the company’s management, certain challenges have also emerged, related to the interactions with the team leaders, impact on the construction and reinforcement of the corporate culture, not-perfectly aligned behaviours of a little sample of workers determining reduction of productivity and loss of quality, availability and attention during the customers’ interactions and services, “normalization” of issues taken for granted.

Thanks to the great attention and sponsorship of the company’s owners and top management, to reduce emerging or potential disadvantages and capitalize on all the benefits experienced from 2017, specific training sessions and courses have been elaborated and developed towards team leaders to reinforce their leadership competences and skills to better manage and engage remote workers and

overall teams and to define and share new organizational “rules” combining clear processes of delegation, attribution of roles and responsibilities, objective to be reached, assessment of performance and behaviours with actions, initiatives and behaviours strongly aimed to create quality and wellness for the employees and a climate of trust in the organization both at horizontal and vertical level.

Accordingly, the capacity to create trust and engagement, emotive knowledge and communication skills emerge as significant traits influencing leadership in a wide and structured context of remote working as in the company Theta. Directive leadership and servant leadership styles can be, consequently, identified as the more fitted styles adopted at Theta, with some minor elements of transformational leadership.

Regarding the evolution of remote working, also in Theta it is perceived as inevitable and the related process as irreversible. However, it is considered desirable and beneficial the elaboration and application of more precise and detailed normative frameworks about remote working according to which setting recruitment, typologies of contracts and industrial relations.

11. Synthesis and implications

In line with the project objectives, the research team conducted an empirical field analysis in 2024, examining the perceptions, awareness, implementation, and practical use of remote working practices in Basilicata, as well as the leadership traits that effectively support the remote working philosophy and model. The identification of companies that systematically use remote working required an in-depth analysis of the local economic landscape and consultation with representative institutions of the business sector, such as Federmanager and Confindustria. The analysis revealed a very limited use of remote working in Basilicata, primarily concentrated in the ICT sector. It also allowed the identification of companies that systematically use remote working at the regional level. These companies do not operate in peripheral or geographically isolated areas, highlighting that this approach reflects a deliberate business strategy, rather than a response to logistical challenges.

The identified companies were contacted and interviewed. The results from the interviews conducted with managers, founders, and entrepreneurs have highlighted a picture that certainly presents unitary traits and threads from which to deduce a specific overall point of view on the remote working situation, although it is possible to underline different nuances within this scenario.

What emerges is that remote working practices in Basilicata are mainly adopted by companies with a mature and established corporate history. These companies have experienced growth over the years in terms of both turnover and employee numbers. The COVID-19 pandemic, from this point of view, was often perceived by these companies as a catalyst for starting a transition process towards a qualitative leap in their organisation. This leap has included the dynamics linked to remote working practices.

Initially adopted as a mere mandatory measure for company operations, remote working has ended up becoming an essential pillar of business re-organization. However, the perception of its need and effectiveness - as well as its adoption - has not been uniformly positive. The spectrum of reactions varies from more typically "techno-enthusiastic" companies, that proactively embrace the benefits of remote work- compensating for the apparent loss of control over the employees and satisfied about the workforce results in terms of productivity, to organizations that are more reluctant to accept these working practices.

A common concern within all the organizations involved in the research is represented by the idea that it is considerably more complex, for employees joining the company from scratch, easily building their active participation in the corporate culture, remotely conveying those values and exemplary

behaviours that progressively cement employees' adherence to a certain value system and professional mentality.

At the same time, a commonly perceived benefit is the possibility of recruiting professionals without geographical constraints. On the one hand, this is an element to increase an organisation's attractiveness and competitiveness within a territory, by allowing access to the specific know-how that is needed and minimizing the training required for employees who may lack certain skills. On the other hand, this dynamic also takes the form of a defensive and preventive measure against internal turnover and external dumping. As highlighted in the interviews, remote working has often allowed ICT organizations to minimize the theft of their human capital by big companies of international importance.

To counteract the challenges inherent in remote working, companies are trying to create alternative moments of conviviality for in-person interactions, sharing organizational culture, impressions, feelings and values. When asked about their chosen leadership style, based on the provided nomenclature, the answers were rather heterogeneous and debated: catalyst, servant and transformational - or a holistic sum of all the leadership styles presented – appear to be the driving methods in which the entrepreneurs and managers who participated in the survey best identified themselves.

Table 2 summarizes the main benefits and challenges of adopting remote working perceived by the investigated companies.

Benefits	Challenges
Increase of productivity and reduction of absenteeism: Higher workforce productivity, greater organizational commitment, and trust between employees and management, with a reduction in absenteeism.	Difficulties in cultural absorption: New employees face greater challenges in absorbing the company's culture, values, and professional mindset.
Access to a broader talent pool: Recruitment is no longer limited by geographic location, allowing access to specialized skills and reducing the need for training.	Challenges in preserving corporate culture: Difficulties in transmitting and aligning the company's values, and challenges in consolidating a strong and shared corporate culture among remote workers
Costs saving: Reduction in costs related to decreased training needs, savings on expenses such as office-related costs, transportation, and energy.	Complex onboarding: Difficulties for new hires to become active participants in corporate culture and internal organizational dynamics.
Talent retention: Preventing turnover and protecting companies from losing staff to international competitors.	Increased workers' isolation and loneliness & risk of techno-stress
Improvement of work-life balance: Enhanced balance between employees' professional and personal lives, with reduced commuting times and greater scheduling flexibility.	Management and monitoring of remote work: Challenges in effectively monitoring and supporting remote employees, particularly concerning teamwork and conflict management
Improvement of the company's reputation	Lack of face-to-face interactions: The absence of physical interaction moments can lead to a reduced sense of belonging and engagement, with potential negative effects on team cohesion and collaboration
	IT security risks

Table 2. The main benefits and challenges of adopting remote working perceived by the investigated companies

Companies share both similar advantages and challenges of remote work. Although they have benefited in terms of improved productivity, recruitment, cost saving, reputation and employee well-being, they face several difficulties related to increased workers' isolation and loneliness, organizational culture absorption and preserving, IT security risks, and remote team management.

To face these difficulties the investigated companies have developed several initiatives often creating meeting, both virtual and in-person, to mitigate negative effects of remote working. In particular, there are several practices that the companies involved in the research are adopting to address the mentioned challenges. These are good practices that - despite the diversity of their business and organizational contexts - have common objectives, such as reducing isolation, strengthening corporate culture, and optimizing remote work performance assessment and management.

Table 3 reports the good practices cited by the companies, clustered by the main objective.

Objective	Good practices implemented by the analyzed companies
Mitigating Isolation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction of "unexpected" elements to alleviate isolation and routine fatigue. • Creation of social events like "Start Days" and CUBE associations to foster connections. • Family-oriented social events to reduce isolation among remote workers. • Hybrid model tailored to employee proximity (remote for those farther away).
Strengthening Corporate Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of hybrid interaction events to reinforce corporate culture.
Performance Assessment and Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meritocratic performance evaluations based on quantitative and qualitative metrics. • Continuous training for team leaders to improve remote team management and engagement.

Table 3 Good practices of the analysed companies

Regarding the traits characterizing an adequate leadership style referred to the adoption of remote working practices, empathy and communication skills emerge as fundamental for maintaining employee trust and engagement, collaboration and organizational cohesion. Certainly, these characteristics are challenging to cultivate and put into practice where daily face-to-face contact is lacking and is filtered through purely virtual forms of interaction.

Figure 1 summarizes the leadership characteristics mentioned by the entrepreneurs and managers interviewed, clustered according to the 4 main categories of leadership competencies in a remote setting identified during the first phase of the research.

Figure 1 Leadership characteristics for remote working in the analyzed companies

Looking ahead to the future of remote working, the process is perceived as inevitable. Conversely, it emerges a strong need to increase the compensation of the same by increasing opportunities for genuine human interaction.

In inner mountain areas, remote working can represent an important opportunity and has great potential to regenerate local economies and communities. However, it must be approached carefully. Good practices, such as creating hybrid remote working spaces, investing in continuous training for managers and entrepreneurs to acquire proper skills for managing remote teams and work, and nurturing a remote working culture, can promote long-term residency, attract expert workers from outside, reduce migration, preserve the survival of local businesses, and ensure their competitiveness. However, to avoid failure, it is crucial to consider local community needs, to avoid focusing merely on attracting remote workers from outside (e.g. digital nomads) and to balance the requests of local development with business growth. It is also important to have managers and entrepreneurs able to address the strategic and operational challenges of remote working. More generally, remote working can contribute to the growth of inner mountain economies and societies only if there is a balance between the opportunities of remote working, the need for sustainable development, and the integration of the local community with its needs and culture.

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Appendix

Questionnaire used

- Domande introduttive – Basic questions about the company profiling

1. Qual è il nome della sua azienda? Name of the company
2. Da quanti anni è attiva? Period of activity
 - A) 0-5 anni/years
 - B) 5-10 anni/years
 - C) 10-30 anni/years
 - D) >30 anni/years
3. In che classe di fatturato si colloca? Range of economic turnover
 - A) <1 milione di euro/millions euros
 - B) 1-5 milioni di euro/ millions euros
 - C) 5-20 milioni di euro/ millions euros
 - D) 20-50 milioni di euro/ millions euros
 - E) >50 milioni di euro/ millions euros
4. Quanti dipendenti ha? Current workforce-number of employees
 - A) 1-10
 - B) 11-50
 - C) 51-250
 - D) >250
5. Qual è il core business della sua azienda? Core-business of the company
6. Qual è il principale mercato di riferimento della sua azienda? Main markets of the company
 - A) Basilicata/Basilicata
 - B) Italia/Italy
 - C) UE/EU
 - D) Extra-UE/EU
7. Può raccontarci in breve la storia e lo sviluppo della sua azienda? Short history of the company
8. Quali sono gli scenari futuri che prevede interesseranno la sua azienda? Scenarios analysis involving the company

- Domande sul remote working e la leadership – Questions about remote working practices and leadership

1. Da quanto tempo la sua azienda attua il remote working? Time of beginning of the adoption of remote working practices
2. Quali sono stati gli eventuali benefici che i dipendenti della sua azienda hanno riscontrato dall'adozione del remote working (è possibile spuntare più di una risposta)/Main benefits of the remote working as lived by the employees (more options possible)
 - A) Miglioramento delle performances lavorative/Improvement of working performances

- B) Soddisfazione lavorativa/Worklife satisfaction
 - C) Equilibrio tra vita lavorativa e personale/Worklife balance
 - D) Riduzione dei livelli di stress/Reduction of stress
 - E) Minimizzazione tempi di spostamento/Reduction of the mobility and commuting times
 - F) Risparmio dei costi legati al trasporto quotidiano/Savings related to mobility and commuting
 - G) Minimizzazione del tasso di abbandono/Reduction of employees' turnover
3. Quali sono stati gli eventuali elementi di criticità che i dipendenti della sua azienda hanno dovuto affrontare in una simile adozione? (è possibile spuntare più di una risposta)/Main concerns of the remote working as lived by the employees (more options possible)
- A) Aumento dell'isolamento e della solitudine/Increase of isolation and loneliness
 - B) Burnout/Burnout
 - C) Tecno-stress/Technostress
 - D) Sovraccarico di informazioni/Information overloading
 - E) Conflitti fra lavoro e famiglia/Conflicts between worklife and family issues
 - F) Abbandono aziendale/Increase of employees' turnover
4. In una scala da 0 a 5, quale valore darebbe a ciascuno degli eventuali benefici per l'azienda derivati dall'adozione del remote working? On a 5-point scale, how could you rate the potential benefits of the remote working for your company as lived by owner/manager?
- A) Contributo all'impegno organizzativo/Engagement
 - B) Riduzione del tasso di assenteismo/Reduction of turnover
 - C) Incremento del processo di standardizzazione delle procedure/Improvement of standardization of the procedures
 - D) Miglioramento della reputazione aziendale/Improvement of the company's reputation
 - E) Facilità nel trovare personale specializzato senza vincoli geografici/Easiness to find and recruit specialized HR without geographical constraints
5. In una scala da 0 a 5, quale valore darebbe a ciascuno degli eventuali svantaggi per l'azienda derivati dall'adozione del remote working? On a 5-point scale, how could you rate the potential disadvantages of the remote working for your company as lived by owner/manager?
- A) Impatto negativo sulla cultura e sui valori organizzativi/Negative impact on organizational culture and values
 - B) Difficoltà nella gestione dei conflitti/Concerns in conflicts management
 - C) Difficoltà nella costruzione del team/Concernes in teambuilding
 - D) Difficoltà nel teamwork e nel coinvolgimento/Concerns in teamworking and engagement
 - E) Difficoltà nel monitorare e supportare i lavoratori remoti/Concerns in monitoring and supporting remote workers
 - F) Riduzione della fiducia reciproca e della fedeltà aziendale/Reduction of trust
 - G) Rischi per la sicurezza informatica dell'azienda/Concerns about cybersecurity
6. Qual è la percentuale di dipendenti della sua azienda che lavora attualmente a distanza?
Percentage of workforce currently in remote working

7. Quali sono le qualità che più influenzano la capacità di essere leader rispetto ad un contesto di remote working (è possibile spuntare più di una risposta)? In your opinion, what are the most important traits influencing the capacity to be leader in a remote working context?
 - A) Coaching/Coaching
 - B) Adattabilità/Adaptability
 - C) Capacità comunicative adeguate/Communication skills
 - D) Intelligenza emotiva/Emotive knowlegde
 - E) Proattività/Proactivity

8. Come definirebbe il suo stile di leadership? How do you define your leadership style?
 - A) Directive leadership
 - B) Catalyst leadership
 - C) Resonant leadership
 - D) Servant leadership
 - E) Transformational leadership
 - F) Authentic leadership
 - G) E-leadership
 - H) Distributed leadership
 - I) Shared leadership

9. Come crede evolverà il remote working, ed il conseguente rapporto con una leadership efficace, nella sua azienda? What is your opinion about the evolution of the practices of remote working and, consequently, the leadership traits and behaviours to be implemented?